

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES DATA

Compound	m.p. °C	%CO	%Halogen	%S	%N	%C	%H	ΔM (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
[Co(NATU) ₂ (Moph) ₂ ClO ₄] ₂ ClO ₄	>300	8.72 (8.87)*	10.56 (10.68)	9.48 (9.62)	12.51 (12.65)	28.68 (28.90)	5.00 (5.14)	153	4.84
[Co(NATU) ₂ (phen) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	>300	6.85 (6.93)	8.25 (8.34)	7.34 (7.52)	13.00 (13.17)	44.88 (45.16)	4.92 (5.08)	242	4.96

* Figures in parenthesis indicate calculated values.

$\nu(\text{CN})$] at 1445 and 1330 cm^{-1} and thionide III [$\nu(\text{CS}) + \nu(\text{CN})$] and [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S}) + \delta(\text{NCS})$] at 935 and 1245 cm^{-1} show a +ve shift, clearly indicating coordination through nitrogen of N-allyl thiourea⁸.

The bands at 3210 and 1100 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$ stretch respectively clearly indicated that one morpholine coordinated through nitrogen and the other through oxygen atom⁹. The band¹⁰ at 1430 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and the bands¹¹ at 840 and 720 cm^{-1} due to C-H out of plane bending vibrations and ring stretching of 1,10-phenanthroline clearly indicated that 1,10-phenanthroline coordinated through both the nitrogen atoms.

In the electronic spectra of phenanthroline complex the bands at ~ 500 , ~ 600 and at 850 nm are assignable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3), ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ (ν_1) indicating the octahedral structure¹¹. For the other complex the bands at 515 (ν_4), 665 (ν_2) and 870 nm (ν_2) values suggest the complex to be penta-coordinated^{12,13}.

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Stabilities and Thermodynamics of Uranyl(II) and Thorium(IV) Complexes of DL-nor-Leucine

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IN continuation of our earlier investigations on the electrochemical behaviour of amino acids and their metal complexes¹⁻⁴, this communication deals with the study of the composition, stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} complexes with DL-nor-leucine for which no reference could be traced in literature.

Experimental

DL-nor-leucine (referred herein as HA) was supplied by B.D.H., Poole, England. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal digital pH-meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly. Conductance was measured on an electronic type conductometer. Temperature was controlled by a universal (U_g -type) thermostat.

pH titrations were carried out in the absence and presence of metal ion against standard (0.1 M) NaOH for establishing the stoichiometry of the complexes formed during the interaction of metal ion and HA. For determining stability constants at 20, 30 and 40°, the ratio of metal to ligand was always one to five (1:5) and 5 mM HClO_4 was used for initial lowering of buffer region. The entire study was carried out in aqueous media at ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO_4 . Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum method was applied to calculate the stability constants of the complexes formed.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The composition of the complexes formed during the interaction of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} with DL-nor-leucine was established by measuring the magnitude of the proton displacement during the titration of the ligand in absence and presence of metal ion in different molar ratios against standard NaOH.

The addition of an equimolar concentration of UO_2^{2+} greatly alters the shape of free-ligand titra-

tion curves (Fig. 1, curve 4) indicating the complex

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of DL-nor-leucine in absence and presence of UO_2^{2+} with 0.1 M NaOH
 Curve (1) 4.0×10^{-3} M HA
 Curve (2) 4.0×10^{-3} M HA + 1.0×10^{-3} M UO_2^{2+}
 Curve (3) 4.0×10^{-3} M HA + 2.0×10^{-3} M UO_2^{2+}
 Curve (4) 4.0×10^{-3} M HA + 4.0×10^{-3} M UO_2^{2+}

formation which results in the lowering of buffer region due to proton displacement

Since the extent of proton displacement depends on the relative affinity of the ligand for H^+ and the metal ion, it is obvious that the interaction of UO_2^{2+} with HA is sufficient to compete with a relatively high $[H^+]$. The inflection at $m=2$ (m being the moles of NaOH per mole of ligand) suggests the formation of $UO_2(A)_2$ as the highest complex in accordance with the following equation :

With the metal ion and the ligand in the ratio 1 : 2, the inflection is obtained at $m=1$ (Fig. 1, curve 3) which corresponds to the formation of $UO_2(A)_2$. Since there is no significant inflection at $m=0.5$, the formation of $UO_2(A)^+$ and $UO_2(A)_2$ must take place with considerable overlapping according to the following equations :

i.e., 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are being formed simultaneously. The inflection at $m=0.5$ (Fig. 1, curve 2) confirms the above conclusion.

Similarly, there is a fall in the initial pH value of the ligand solutions with the addition of an equimolar concentration of Th^{4+} ions showing the complex formation

The inflection at $m=4$ may suggest the formation of either $Th(A)(OH)_3$ or $Th(A)_4$ and $Th(OH)_4$ in accordance with the following equations :

The appearance of precipitate during the titration rules out the possibility of formation of hydroxo metal complexes⁵ as indicated by equation (7) and supports the formation of $Th(A)_4$ and $Th(OH)_4$.

The inflection at $m=1$ corresponding to the ratio of 1 : 4 confirms the formation of $Th(A)_4$ as the highest complex in accordance with the following equation :

The conductometric titrations yield breaks corresponding to the formation of complexes obtained by potentiometric technique.

Stability constants : Calvin and Melchior's⁶ extension of Bjerrum's method⁷ has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complexes at 20, 30 and 40° and ionic strength $\mu=0.1$ M $NaClO_4$ and their values are given in Table 1. The formation curves obtained at different temperatures by plotting $\bar{n}$ vs $-\log[A]$ (Fig. 2) reveal the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes for UO_2^{2+} -HA system and 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 complexes for the Th^{4+} -HA system.

Fig. 2. Formation curves at 20, 30 and 40° for UO_2^{2+} complexes of DL-nor-leucine.

Thermodynamic functions : The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation reactions have been determined at 30° with the help of Gibbs Helmholtz and isobar equation⁸, $\Delta G = -RT \log \beta$, and recorded in Table 1. ΔH is determined with the help of an isobar $\frac{d(\log \beta)}{d(1/T)} = \frac{-\Delta H}{4.57}$. ΔS is then evaluated from the relation $\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$.

It is observed from Table 1 that the values of stability constants of UO_2^{2+} complexes decrease

with increase in temperature showing that the complexation reaction is exothermic; whereas in the case of Th^{4+} complexes, the $\log K_{\text{stab}}$ values increase with temperature indicating an endothermic process. These observations are confirmed by -ve value of ΔH in the case of UO_2^{2+} complex and positive ΔH in the case of Th^{4+} complexes. This explains the variation of stability constants with temperature for the two metal ions in opposite direction (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log \beta$ vs $\frac{1}{T}$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ AND $\text{Th}(\text{IV})$ COMPLEXES OF DL-NOR-LEUCINE AT $\mu = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4)

Constants* and thermodynamic functions	$\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ complexes			$\text{Th}(\text{IV})$ complexes		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
$\log K_1$	7.81	7.72	7.61	—	—	—
$\log K_2$	6.92	6.72	6.62	8.52	8.57	8.62
$\log K_3$				8.20	8.23	8.27
$\log K_4$				4.99	5.49	5.99
ΔG (Kcal/mole)		-20.02			-30.90	
ΔH (Kcal/mole)		-10.38			24.48	
ΔS (cal/deg/mole)		31.81			182.77	

* Uncertainty limit ± 0.02

The negative values of ΔG in both cases indicate that the reaction proceeds spontaneously.

The positive ΔS values (Table 1) obtained indicate that entropy factor strongly favours the chelate formation, and stabilises the complex due to the liberation of water molecules from the ion accompanying complexation.

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Stability and Thermodynamic Constants of Some Alkaline Earth Salts of Adrenalinatate Ion

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ADRENALINE (epinephrine) is 1-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-methyl amino ethanol and is used as a vasoconstrictor. With the belief that metal complexes play an important part in the biological activity of drugs¹, as most of the drugs possess chelating structures initially or after metabolic alterations, much work has been done to study the avidity of various drugs for metals. Study of chelation of catechol amines with some transition metals has been reported earlier²⁻⁵. But no information is available on chelation of M^{2+} ions with adrenaline. In this communication we report the results of our studies on M^{2+} -adrenaline complexes, where $\text{M}^{2+} = \text{Be}^{2+}$, Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+} .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of high purity analytical grade. The preparation and standardisation of the metal ion and the ligand solutions and the experimental details are the same as reported earlier⁶.

Stoichiometry of the complexes formed was ascertained by conductometric titrations. The Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique⁶ as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ was followed to determine various formation constants at three temperatures, 0, 25 and 37° and at a fixed ionic strength of 0.1 M with KCl. The experimental procedure consists in titration of the following thermostated mixtures of solutions with a 0.2 M alkali solution.

- (i) 5 ml of 0.02 M HCl solution,
- (ii) Solution (i) + 10 ml of 0.01 M adrenaline solution,
- (iii) Mixture (ii) + 5 ml of 0.002 M metal ion solution.

The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at 0.1 M by adding the required quantity of 1.0 M KCl solution, keeping the total volume at 50 ml with double distilled water.

The values of $\bar{n}H$, $\bar{n}$ and pL^- were calculated using the Irving-Rossotti equations⁷, and the values